

Investigation of Active Electrocatalytic Centers Under Reaction Conditions Using Operando Microscopies

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Abstract

Electrocatalysis is crucial for transitioning from a fossil fuel-based to a renewable energy society. In situ identification of electrocatalytic active centers is required to realize this vision, enabling the design of efficient and stable catalysts and providing insight into reaction steps. In this manuscript, we analyze the recent progress in the observation of active sites in a wide range of electrocatalysts and various electrocatalytic reactions by employing operando microscopies, including liquid cell transmission electron microscopy (LCTEM), electrochemical scanning tunneling microscopy (EC-STM), scanning electrochemical microscopy (SECM) and scanning electrochemical cell microscopy (SECCM). We showcase their capability to correlate the electrocatalytic activity with catalyst topological and structural properties.

Keywords:

In situ experiments, operando microscopy, active electrocatalytic sites, catalyst surface, electrocatalytic activity

1. Introduction

Electrocatalysis plays a crucial role in energy conversion and storage applications. [1, 2, 3] To gain an in-depth understanding of the reaction mechanism and optimize the catalyst, identification of the active centers is essential. [4, 5, 6, 7] Considering that a severe reaction environment could cause surface transformations, operando microscopies are regarded very important since they allow direct monitoring of catalyst behavior and reveal active sites under operating conditions. [8, 9, 10] Nowadays, with the advancement of characterization technology, catalyst surfaces can be investigated more accurately and intuitively in real-time and often at the atomic level. [11, 12, 13, 14]

This manuscript provides an overview of advanced experimental techniques that enable the characterization of active electrocatalytic centers under reaction conditions. We start with recent examples involving liquid cell transmission electron microscopy (LCTEM) followed by electrochemical scanning tunneling microscopy (EC-STM) novel applications, where the so-called atomic resolution of active centers is frequently possible. The following section presents microscopies enabling the explicit monitoring and quantification of the electrocatalytic activity, including scanning electrochemical microscopy (SECM) and scanning electrochemical cell microscopy (SECCM).

2. Liquid Cell Transmission Electron Microscopy (LCTEM)

LCTEM is an important tool that employs thin-film electrodes on chips to visualize dynamic processes within a static or flowing liquid environment. [15, 16, 17, 18, 19] With the rapid development of nanofabrication and micro-electromechanical system (MEMS) manufacturing technology, it is possible to obtain valuable information about the structural and morphological evolutions of studied materials as well as electrochemical processes in real-time under working conditions [20, 21, 22, 23, 24].

The structure and morphology of the catalyst play an important role in the catalytic performance, influencing activity as well as selectivity toward final products. For instance, Grosse et al. recently showed the applicability of the LCTEM methodology in electrochemistry by linking the real-time restructuring of various copper (I) oxide cubes during the reaction to the catalytic selectivity of the CO₂ reduction reaction (CO₂RR). [25] They electrochemically synthesized Cu₂O cubes of various initial sizes and loadings and tracked the reaction products in real-time for several hours during CO₂RR. **Figure 1a** depicts the morphological alteration of the cubic catalysts at -0.9 V_{RHE} in CO₂-saturated 0.1 M KHCO₃. The larger cubes (390 nm and 170 nm cubes) are mostly stable, while the smaller cubes (80 nm cubes) show higher mobility and a significant decrease in number, indicating catalyst detachment and aggregation over time. Furthermore, all cubes experience surface roughening during reaction conditions, resulting in the formation of small particles (NPs), which subsequently re-deposit onto the cube surfaces as nanoparticles (NPs). By investigating these morphological changes in real-time during the reaction, the highest selectivity towards the desired multi-carbon products, such as C₂H₄, is achieved neither by the biggest nor the smallest Cu₂O cubes. A combination of a high density of cubes with a high density of re-deposited NPs for the 170 nm cubes results in the best C₂₊ product selectivity and stability, emphasizing the power of this methodology in identifying and understanding active catalyst materials and their morphological evolution during the reaction, which is only rarely considered

in electrochemistry. Moreover, some works on investigating degradation mechanisms of supported Pt-based nanocatalysts in proton exchange membrane fuel cells (PEMFCs) have been reported by using LCTEM [26, 27], which unambiguously revealed the dynamic movement of NPs during electrochemical cycling, as shown in **Figure 1b**. The different aging processes of particle detachment, coalescence, dissolution, precipitation, migration, etc., were appreciably detected after different testing cycles under real-time and operando conditions. This technique provides a new visual understanding of tracking the dynamics of nanocatalysts in PEMFCs during operation.

Figure 1. (a) Real-time morphological alteration of Cu_2O cubes under reaction conditions of CO_2RR by EC-TEM of 390 nm, 170 nm, and 80 nm cubes. Snapshots are extracted from the videos during EC-TEM at 0, 5, 25, and 45 mins of applying $-0.9 V_{\text{RHE}}$. Adapted with permission from ref. [25]. Copyright 2021 Springer Nature. (b) Different degrading processes for supported Pt NPs at various potentials. The squares correspond to detachment (orange), coalescence (green), precipitation (purple), partial dissolution (yellow), migration (green), and precipitation (red), respectively. Adapted with permission from ref. [26]. Copyright 2020 American

3. Electrochemical Scanning Tunneling Microscopy (EC-STM)

Another powerful tool to reveal active centers on catalysts is the EC-STM by detecting the local noise level or “roughness” of the tunneling current. The first approach was presented by Pfisterer et al. in 2017, recording continuous changes in the electrochemical properties of electrolytes within the tunneling barrier at active sites. [28, 29, 30] The location of active sites for different reactions can be investigated on a wide range of catalytic materials [31, 32, 33, 34]. The tunneling current of an active step edge (red line) and a region of defects (blue line) with inactive sites (black line) were compared on highly ordered pyrolytic graphite (HOPG) for the hydrogen evolution reaction (HER), illustrated in **Figure 2a**. [35] The higher tunneling current near the step edge and in the defective area implies the position of the active sites. A recently published study performed noise measurements on freshly annealed Pd(111) in 0.1M HClO₄. [36] Here, to obtain a reliable conclusion about the activity of the individual basal plane, the crystals were annealed in the absence of oxygen and measured with a Pt quasi-reference electrode and a Pd counter electrode. **Figure 2b** exhibits the geometry of four steps with different heights separated by two atomically flat terraces. Various noise levels indicate that the contiguous atomically flat areas are slightly active, while the highest activity is measured on steps consisting of several atomic layers. Interestingly, the authors present an alteration of the surface morphology after performing cyclic voltammetry measurements even after only a few cycles, which is presumably caused by hydrogen absorption and thus the formation of Pd-hydrides within the bulk. As a result, active sites are visible on both concave and convex sites for Pd(111) and are no longer mainly on step edges. Furthermore, there are also some materials where the noise level is homogeneously distributed throughout the whole surface morphology when the reaction is turned on, without showing any active area. This is the case for the oxygen reduction reaction (ORR) on the Pt₃Ni(111) surface in 0.1 M HClO₄ (**Figure 2c**) [37].

Instead of analyzing the topographic structural differences on top of presumably active sites, EC-STM experiments can also utilize the difference between the set current value and the actual measured tunneling current to show at what potential values certain sites become active. [38] Kosmala et al. first presented this approach in 2021 and proved its application to explore the HER activity of single defects and complex structures with atomic-scale resolution. [39] Several structural topographies can be observed in **Figure 2d**: graphene covered the Pt(111) surface, graphene covered the Fe basal plane (black rectangle) and corresponding step edges (yellow rectangle), also Fe filled C vacancies (other rectangles). By comparing the current roughness of different topographies (**Figure 2e**), they pinpoint that the most active sites are Fe atoms trapped in C vacancies, followed by the Fe step edge. At the same time, the Fe basal plane is less active. These results agree with density functional theory (DFT) calculations. Moreover, the W-filled Se vacancies as point defects on a WSe₂-coated Au(111) surface for HER were investigated by Lunardon et al. [40]. With the applied electrochemical potential, a significant increase in signal perturbation and current roughness is indicative of the high activity at point defect sites (**Figure 2f**).

Figure 2. (a) EC-STM measurements for HER on HOPG, showing the higher activity on step edge and defects compared to the basal plane. Reprinted with permission from ref. [35]. Copyright 1999 Royal Society of Chemistry. (b) 3D n-EC-STM image of freshly annealed Pd(111) and corresponding line scans. According to noise spikes, active step sites and inactive terraces were visualized. Reprinted with permission from ref. [36]. Copyright 2022 Small published by Wiley-VCH GmbH. (c) EC-STM measurements for ORR on the Pt₃Ni(111) surface in 0.1 M HClO₄. The noise level seems homogeneous throughout the surface terraces. Reprinted with permission from ref. [37]. Copyright 2008 Royal Society of Chemistry. (d) EC-STM tomographic schematics of the graphene/Fe (1.8 ML)/Pt(111) surface at $E = 195 \text{ mV}_{\text{RHE}}$. (e) The current roughness analysis with various potentials exhibits the activity on different sites. (d) & (e) reprinted with permission from ref. [39]. Copyright 2018 Springer Nature BV. (f) Point defect in the WSe₂ layer on top of Au(111) and comparison of the tunneling currents of the point

defect at different applied potentials. Adapted with permission from ref. [40]. Copyright 2017 Elsevier Science & Technology Journals.

4. Scanning Electrochemical Microscopy (SECM) and Scanning Electrochemical Cell Microscopy (SECCM)

SECM allows the identification of active centers by observing electrochemical reactions at nanoscales. This evaluation is accomplished using an ultra-small nanoelectrode approach and subsequent scanning of the sample surface. The current measured at the electrode mainly reflects faradaic processes and the electrode tip's distance from the sample [41]. Sun et al. successfully identified the active sites for the oxygen evolution reaction (OER) on semi-2D NiO nanosheets, which contained defect holes immobilized on HOPG. This identification was possible by combining feedback [42] and sample generation/tip collection (SG/TC) [43] modes to obtain topographical and local electrocatalytic information independently. **Figure 3a** and **Figure 3b** depict images derived from these modes, explicitly demonstrating the increased activity of the edges compared to fully coordinated surfaces [44]. Besides, Sun et al. identified the HER active sites for solution-exfoliated MoS₂ nanosheets on indium tin oxide (ITO) using electrodes smaller than 20 nm [45]. Wang et al. integrated an advanced dual-pass scan mode with thermal drift calibration software and superior hardware structure to achieve exceptional spatial and temporal resolution, termed fast scan mode [46]. **Figure 3c** and **Figure 3d** showcase the 3D color map of the feedback mode topographical image and the SG/TC mode HER activity map at fast scan mode of a 2H MoS₂/HOPG transition region. Due to the accelerated scanning rate (1600 nm/s), the temporal resolution improves significantly, which limits hydrogen diffusion into the electrolyte and thereby prevents signal broadening, enabling a more accurate image and a precise determination of active sites.

It is worth noting that the hybrid technique AFM-SECM, which integrates SECM with atomic force microscopy, has attracted the attention of researchers since it combines the merits of SECM for recording

electrochemical current mapping with the capability of AFM for detecting surface morphology. [47, 48, 49] Therefore, it is widely applied to distinguish between sites with various catalytic properties. Schechter et al. [50] exploited the ORR activity of three Pt-nanoaggregates (NAs) in different sizes and structures on the HOPG surface by AFM-SECM at a spatial resolution of 16 nm (**Figure 3e**). The position of these Pt-NAs is clearly visible by the height profile; the current mapping and the corresponding current distribution at 0.73 V_{SHE} indicate high reaction activity on NAs 1 and 2, but no noticeable activity on NA 3. The electrochemical activity relies not only on the size and structure but also on the shape and exposed facet. Based on their observation, Ma et al. [51] revealed the effects of different Cu₂O nanocrystal facets on the interactions between electrolyte and electrode. Combined with the DFT results, it is concluded that the (111) facet on Cu₂O exhibited higher surface energy and superior electron transfer.

SECCM is another advanced tool that can simultaneously visualize the electrochemical activity and topographical variation at interfaces and thereby elucidate active sites. [52, 53, 54] Distinct from the SECM, the electrolyte is confined in a nanopipette of the SECCM to avoid the material's immersion in the solution. Each electrochemical measurement can be locally and independently performed within a well-defined small droplet created at the tip of the probe. Diverse electrocatalytic reactions have been recently investigated, including HER [55, 56, 57, 58, 59], OER [60], ORR [61, 62, 63] and CO₂RR [64]. SECCM chronoamperometry has been employed for revealing the local OER activity of single-crystalline β-Co(OH)₂ particles by Chueh and co-workers. [65] Mapping local OER current density across the surface (yellow dot lines in **Figure 3f**) shows that only the edge facets of particles contribute to the current, while the basal planes are inactive. Liu et al. recorded the topography and HER activity of a 45 nm self-assembled Au NPs monolayer. [66] The results demonstrate the higher activity of Au NPs compared to the Au substrate electrode and

heterogeneous activity on the monolayer due to random Au NP arrangement (**Figure 3g**). In addition, by combining SECCM with collocated electron backscatter diffraction, the structure-activity correlation has been explored at individual crystallographic orientations and grain boundaries on polycrystalline surfaces. [67,68]

Figure 3. Feedback mode (a) and SG/TC mode (b) images of semi-2D NiO, which contained defect holes immobilized on HOPG. Reprinted with permission from ref. [44]. The feedback mode image of a 2H MoS₂/HOPG transition region is illustrated in 3D (c), while SG/TC mode image was recorded at a scan rate of 1600 nm/s (d). Adapted with permission from ref. [46]. Copyright 2008 Springer Nature BV. (e) AFM-SECM height profile and current mapping of three Pt-NAs with different sizes and structures on HOPG at 0.73 V_{SHE}, close to the onset potential of the ORR reaction. Adapted with permission from ref. [50]. Copyright 1992 Elsevier Science & Technology Journals. (f) Tip current density and z position as a function of x position in scanning constant height mode for the single crystalline β -Co(OH)₂

particles. Adapted with permission from ref. [65]. Copyright 1995 Springer Nature BV. (g) Topography and electrochemical HER activity schematics of Au NP self-assembled monolayer. Reprinted with permission from ref. [66]. Copyright 2022 American Chemical Society.

5. Summary and Outlook

In this manuscript, we focused on rapidly developing operando microscopies, mainly LCTEM, EC-STM, SECM, and SECCM, and emphasized their capabilities in electrocatalysis, especially the ability to identify electrochemical active centers in a wide range of electrocatalysts and various electrochemical reactions. They construct a bridge between topographical information and electrochemical activity and provide new possibilities for the rational design of the catalyst and the comprehension of the reaction pathways. **Table 1** and **Figure 4** summarize the location of active sites with the corresponding catalyst material, electrolyte, and reaction from recent studies. However, their limitations should also be taken into account. Spatial resolution and temporal resolution are two of the most noteworthy challenges, depending on the tip size and probe scanning speed, respectively. Moreover, to further expand their applications, the combination of these microscopies with other relevant techniques can provide more complete information about chemical and physical properties under reaction conditions.

Table 1 Summary of active site position with the corresponding catalyst material, electrolyte, and reaction

Reaction	Material	Electrolyte	Location of active sites	Method	Ref.
HER	Au(111)	0.1 M HClO ₄	edge site (negative than -90 mV _{RHE}), terrace site (negative than -115 mV _{RHE})	EC-STM	40
HER	Pd nanoparticles on HOPG	0.1 M HClO ₄	highest activity for Pd NPs with a diameter of ~3.4 nm	EC-STM	40
HER	W filled Se vacancies on a WSe ₂ coated Au(111)	0.1 M HClO ₄	point defects	EC-STM	40
ORR	Pt(111) with step defect	0.1 M HClO ₄	step defect (concave sites at the steps) shows higher activity than terraces	EC-STM	31
ORR	Pt(111)	0.1 M LiOH	Pt(111) terraces	EC-STM	31
ORR	Pt(111)	0.1 M KOH	Pt(111) terraces	EC-STM	31
ORR	Pt(111)	0.1 M CsOH	Pt(111) terraces	EC-STM	Fehler! Textmarkerke nicht definiert

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HER	Iron films covered with a monolayer graphene on Pt(111)	0.1 M HClO ₄	point defects based on iron atoms trapped into vacancy clusters are the most active sites followed by the iron step edge and the iron basal plane covered by graphene	EC-STM	39
HER	Pd(100)	0.1 M HClO ₄	step edges, slightly on terraces	EC-STM	36
HER	Pd(100) after cycling	0.1 M HClO ₄	convex area shows higher activity	EC-STM	36
HER	Pd(111)	0.1 M HClO ₄	upper step edge	EC-STM	36
HER	Pd(111) after cycling	0.1 M HClO ₄	all over the surface	EC-STM	36
HER	Pd overlayer on Au (111)	0.1 M H ₂ SO ₄	Pd atoms located close to the boundary	EC-STM	69
HER	Pt monoatomic-thick 2D island on Au(111)	0.1 M HClO ₄	predominantly over the Pt atoms	EC-STM	69
HER	HOPG	0.1 M HClO ₄	in the vicinity of step edges on the upper side and defective sites	EC-STM	35
ORR	Pt ₃ Ni(111)	0.1 M HClO ₄	terrace and step sites contribute comparably to the overall activity	EC-STM	37
HER and ORR	Pt(111)	0.1 M HClO ₄	step-like defects are more active than terraces	EC-STM	30
HER	Monoatomically high islands of Pd on Au(111)	0.1 M H ₂ SO ₄	activity order: only a few Pd atoms close to the boundary > Pd island > Au substrate	EC-STM	30

ORR	HOPG	0.1 M KOH	upper edge of the steps	EC-STM	33
OER	HOPG	0.1 M KOH	upper step edge, and terrace sites only at high potential $0.9V_{Pt}$	EC-STM	33
OER	Amorphous IrO _x electrochemically grown on Ir(111)	0.1 M HClO ₄	step and terrace sites are comparably active	EC-STM	34
ORR	Polycrystalline Pt ₅ Gd and Pt ₅ Pr	0.1 M HClO ₄	step top and terrace sites are more active than step bottom	EC-STM	70
HER	HOPG	0.1 M HClO ₄	upper edge of the step	EC-STM	32
OER	semi-2D NiO with defect holes on HOPG	1 mM KOH, 0.1 M KCl, 1 mM Fc	edge sites	SECM	44
HER	2H MoS ₂ /HOPG transition region	10 mM KOH, 0.1 M KCl, 1 mM Fc	edge sites	SECM	46
ORR	Pt-nanoparticles on HOPG	0.1 M HClO ₄	particles of 300 nm or less	AFM- SECM	50
ORR	Complex solid solution: Ag ₁ Ir ₁₇ Pd ₅₆ Pt ₁₅ Ru ₁₁	0.1 M HClO ₄	~29,000 sites contribute to the measured electrocatalytic current with a ~50 nm probe size	SECCM	62
HER	Self-assembled Au	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	higher activity of Au NPs than that of the Au	SECCM	66

	nanoparticles monolayer		substrate electrode		
CO ₂ RR	Sn particles deposited on reduced graphene oxide	0.1 M KHCO ₃	interface between the Sn particle and rGO, but also slightly on Sn particles	SECCM	64
OER	β -Co(OH) ₂ particles	0.1 M KOH	particle edge facets	SECCM	65
HER	N-doped graphene oxide at an ITO slide	2 M H ₂ SO ₄	activity order: N-rGO edge > N-rGO surface > ITO surface	SECCM	56
HER	Pt nanoparticles at the buried HOPG/Nafion interface	25 mM HClO ₄	enhanced current at the positions of PtNPs at the interface, variations in current between individual PtNPs and Nafion thickness	SECCM	71
HER	Au {100} nanocubes and {111} nano- octahedra	0.1 M HClO ₄	Au NCs are catalytically more active compared to Au ODs	SECCM	63
HER	1H-MoS ₂ nanosheets on HOPG	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	at the edge region of nanosheets	SECCM	59
OER	Hematite (α -Fe ₂ O ₃) nanorods	10 mM NaOH	higher activity at the body portion compared to the tip portion	SECCM	60
HER	natural molybdenite 2H-MoS ₂	0.1 M HClO ₄	activity order: step edges > basal plane between two step edges > basal planes	SECCM	72
OER	ZIF-67-derived Co-	50 mM KOH	an increase in the OER activity with the	SECCM	73

	N-doped C composite particles on GC		number of nanocomposite units		
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Figure 4. Summary of active site position from studies listed in Table 1.

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